
SEASONAL VARIATION IN HEAVY METAL COMPOSITIONAL PROPERTIES OF GROUNDWATER RESERVOIRS IN AKWA-IBOM STATE OF NIGERIA FOR QUALITY EVALUATION

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Abstract: *This work paints a 'broad brush' picture of the water quality of groundwater reservoirs with respect to heavy metals compositional properties before observable changes in the seasons of dry and wet periods. Thus, the underground water variation status of Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria, in West Africa, was evaluated with respect to heavy metal composition in its reservoirs, for consumptive safety validation. A total of 108 water samples were collected from the reservoirs through bore holes at nine research locations (three zones of three sub locations with twelve units), during two major periods of dry and wet seasons. These were analytically used to examine the existence levels of heavy metals of iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), and chromium (Cr) in the water samples from the underground reservoirs of the studied area. The results were compared with the regulatory monitory water standard for quality evaluation. It was found that most of the heavy metals were within Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) and World Health Organization (WHO) water safety limits. And, the variations were: Fe (-0.04 to 0.28), Zn (0.11 to 0.27), Mn (0.02 to 0.11), Cd (0.007 to 0.04), Pb (-0.11 to - 0.09), Cu (-1.92 to 0.05), and Cr (0.21 to 2.68). Treatment for improvement was recommended based on the findings.*

Keywords: *Seasonal Variations, Reservoirs, Pollution, Heavy Metals, Akwa Ibom, etc.*

I. Introduction

Pollution is a popular factor in soil and water conservation and management. Groundwater contamination is a global problem calling for possible resolution (Li *et al.*, 2021). Its impact extends to Nigeria, Africa, and various global water reserves. Natural water contains different types of impurities which are introduced into the aquatic system in different ways, including weathering of rocks and leaching of soils, dissolution of aerosol particles from the atmosphere, and from several human activities, mining, processing, and the use of metal-based materials (Edet A., 2016). Pollutants and/or contaminants affect water quality and safety. Li *et al.* (2021) acknowledged that

understanding the seasonal and spatial variations in groundwater quality is essential for the protection of human health and to maintain crop yields. The uses of water are enormous and beneficial to mankind. According to Ozioko *et al.* (2024), water plays a crucial role in both domestic and industrial settings, and changes in its composition are of great interest. Previous studies on heavy metal contamination with seasonal variation remain non-existent, like the works of Tum *et al.* (2023), Rahi *et al.* (2024), Al-Tamimi *et al.* (2025), *etc.* The research aim of this work, along with the expectation that the groundwater reservoir properties may vary with respect to the periods of dry and wet seasons. Thus, a primary objective of this research was to evaluate these changes occurred during these two periods.

Seasonal Variation refers to the natural changes arising from modification in climate attributes with respect to weather. Season defines the division in a year. Globally, the four divisions of a year are: spring, summer, autumn (fall) and winter seasons. Spring takes place between winter and summer, during which plants springs out of the soil within March to May in the northern continental hemisphere and September to November in the southern continental hemisphere. Summer refer to the time of a year attributive to the months of December to February in the world southern hemisphere when the sun produces highest atmospheric temperatures causing hottest days due to earth inclination and lag in thermal condition. Winter is the time of a year attributive to months of June to August in the world southern continental hemisphere, when the sun is lowest in the sky, thereby producing short days, and lowest atmospheric temperatures for the area. In the world northern continental hemisphere, the attributive months of winter are December to March while summer varies regionally, for example, it occurs within June to August in United Kingdom and June to September in some areas in United States. Autumn or fall takes place between summer and winter (Met, 2025), regardly as a season of change, when temperature begins to drops. It occurs within September to December. In Nigeria, season is divided into dry and wet periods, pointing towards summer and winter with respect to precipitation and temperature. Climatologists usually use full months to represent the seasons (NCSU, 2025). In Nigeria at large, it is divided into six (6) months of dry (no rain) season from November to March, and six (6) months of wet (rainy) season from April to October, in a bimodal sequence. The northeast trade winds producing fine dust - wind from the Sahara locally called the harmattan occur within December to February. This seasonal wind contributes to air pollution, but also environmentally beneficial.

Reservoir is a place where anything is kept in store, or a supply or source of something. In hydro context, it refers to water storage mediums. It may be natural (by nature) or artificial (by manmade). Natural reservoirs include oceans, glaciers and ice sheets, groundwater, lakes, soil moisture, wetlands, living organisms, the atmosphere, and rivers (Okolotu *et al.*, 2024). Denchak, (2023) narrated that "When rain falls and seeps deep into the earth, filling the cracks, crevices, and porous

spaces of an aquifer (basically an underground storehouse of water), it becomes groundwater - one of our least visible but most important natural resources". Water travels through the hydrological cycle in various ways (Okolotu *et al.*, 2025), permitting transfer of some attributes. Facilitatively, Increase in ground water level leads to increase in the depth of other water bodies (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021), and vice versa, providing the medium for exchange of pollutants. Thus, groundwater reserves exchange seepage with surface reservoirs like streams, lakes, oceans, *etc.*, alongside with the possessed contaminants. Approximately 70 % of planet earth is covered by water with only 2.5 % of freshwater, of which 30% is groundwater and the rest is in the form of ice in glaciers and permafrost (Aranguren-Díaz *et al.*, 2024). Earth water storage reserves otherwise reservoirs are of various classes or types irrespective of the nature of formation (natural or artificial). Service reservoirs, sometimes called cisterns, are entirely artificial, dug in underground caverns or elevated high above ground in a water tower to hold clean water while relying on no damming of river or lake (NGS, 2025a). Groundwater (surface, subsurface, *etc*) reservoirs provide more services with a supportive medium. In surface water body reservoirs, most reservoirs are formed by constructing dams across rivers to control the water level by controlling the amount of water that flows out of the reservoir (NGS, 2025a). Water storage facilities have been in existence for thousands of years now. The oldest known dam in the world is the Jawa Dam in now Jordan, built in about 3000 B.C.E. to store water for crop irrigation (NGS, 2025a). Examples of groundwater reservoir at three different layers denoted by types of aquifer are presented in figure one (1) below;

Figure 1: Groundwater reservoir properties (Aranguren-Díaz *et al.*, 2024)

Pollution is synonymously referred to as contamination. Each year, humans generate more than 2 billion tons of waste (NGS, 2025b), which are pollutants. These pollutants or surface contaminants, through percolation and other means within the transport cycle sometimes, find their way to the groundwater reserves (as liquid, or, in mixture of it). Others get trap within the soil (in form of solids), while the rest travel to the atmosphere (in form of gas). Pollution refers to the existence of pollutants (gas, solid, or liquid) in various environmental media. Pollution is categorized environmentally according to the habitation media of air, land, or water related. Air pollution is currently the biggest environmental health risk, killing an estimated 7 million people per year, (UNDRR, 2020). Air pollution is divided into natural sources like dust storms, volcanic activity, gas emission, *etc.*, and man-made otherwise anthropogenic. Soil pollution refers to the contamination of the soil environment by poisonous substances. It is estimated that 25 million agricultural workers per year are affected by pesticide poisoning (Munzel *et al.*, 2023), excluding the numbers affected through other soil related means. Water pollution refers to the contamination of any water medium, in respect to the reduction of its quality, below a set standard. Water is easily polluted because it is a universal solvent with capability of dissolving more substances than any other liquid on earth. The amount of pollutants in the water determines its suitability for human usage such as drinking, bathing, and agriculture (UNDRR, 2020). Denchak, (2023) reported that "Unsafe water kills more people each year than war and all other forms of violence combined". More than 200 organic contaminants have been detected in groundwater, and this number continues to increase (Li *et al.*, 2021).

Heavy Metals refer to sets of dangerous metallic minerals that pose threat to human consumption at notable quantities. Heavy metals are those elements possessing atomic numbers greater than 20 and atomic density above 5 g cm^{-3} as well as exhibit the properties of metal (Raychaudhuri *et al.*, 2021). They are metals regarded as heavy due to their high atomic weights. Heavy metals are chemicals often regarded as tiny pollutants. Examples of these metals include iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), and, chromium (Cr). Lead and mercury are mainly emitted from combustion processes and industrial activities and are toxic to ecosystems as much as they pollute the air (EEA, 2025). Heavy metals are nonbiodegradable naturally and have tendency to accumulate in humans and other living beings (animals and plants). Upon continuous consumption they are dangerously toxic, posing various health hazards at long term. Naturally, heavy metals are categorized into essential like Cu, Ni, Fe, and Zn, and nonessential metals like Cd, Pb and Hg. The human body requires low amounts of some heavy metal ions such as Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} for growth and good health, though high levels of them are toxic, and, some of them including Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , As^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , are considered as contaminants and toxic substances even at very low concentrations (Shadman *et al.*, 2019). They are parts of metalloids and metals in the chemical

periodic table (Iron, cobalt, copper, manganese, zinc, selenium, lead, mercury, arsenic, cadmium, etc). The sources of heavy metals, and heavy metals impact on human health are presented in figures two (2) and three (3) below;

Figure 2: Sources of heavy metals (Moghadas *et al.*, 2022)

A typical heavy metals impact on human health is presented in figure three (3) below;

Figure 3: Impacts of heavy metals toxicity on human health (Aziz *et al.*, 2023)

II. Materials

The study area is Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria in west Africa. Akwa Ibom State was created on the 23rd of September 1987 by General Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida (GAS, 2025). The state covers an area of about 7081 km² extending between latitudes 4°30' and 5°30' north and longitudes 7°30' and 8°20' east. It geographically borders with Rivers State and Abia State to the west and north-west, Cross River State to the east, and the Atlantic Ocean to the south. Akwa Ibom state is geologically underlain with late cretaceous to quaternary sediments. Throughout the Paleocene to early Eocene, thick shale intercalated with sandstone and limestone were deposited (Imo shale formation), (Okunlola & Egbulem, 2015). The formation is over 90 percent sandstone with silicon as the dominant element. The location of the study area is presented in figure four (4)

Figure 4: Akwa Ibom state map (GAS, 2017), & map showing Akwa Ibom in Nigeria

Other materials and equipments used during the study include: Water samples (the medium for testing), Polythene bottles (used to contain the water samples), Ice block container with plastic coolers (used to preserve the natural quality of the samples for correct testing results), Pipette (used to transport measured volume of the water samples), Measuring cylinder (used to measure the volume of the water samples), Conical flask (used to measure the volume of the samples), *etc.*

III. Methods

Total of 108 water samples were collected from twelve (12) boreholes each at various nine locations for a period of one year for laboratory analysis of heavy metal concentration, for the variation in dry and wet seasons. This drafted aim was achieved following long time groundwater heavy metal level

monitoring undertaken on monthly basis prior groundwater extraction through pumping procedures, and, upon nitrate acid digestion, the metal levels of iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), and chromium (Cr) concentration in the groundwater samples were obtained using spectrophotometer technique. Atomic absorption spectrophotometry was recognized by WHO, (2003) as the most widely used method for the determination of water contaminants of heavy metals category. Furthermore, the statistical analysis of mean was deployed in attaining the values from all zones of the area.

IV. Results

Results obtained from the course of this work are presented in tables one (1) to seven (7) and figures five (5) to eight (8) below;

Table 1: Results of sampling, zoning, and locations.

<i>Sample Number</i>	<i>Zone</i>	<i>Location</i>
1	1	Ikot Abasi
2		Ibeno
3		Eket
4	2	Abak
5		Uyo
6		Etinan
7	3	Ikono
8		Ibiono
9		Itu

Table 2: Results of heavy metal levels in the reservoirs during dry season

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Zone</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>Zn</i>	<i>Mn</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Pb</i>	<i>Cu</i>	<i>Cr</i>
1	1	1.30	0.87	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.77
2	2	0.92	0.70	0.07	0.04	0.01	0.08	2.57
3	3	1.01	0.94	0.14	0.05	0.01	0.08	2.73
4	Average	1.08	0.84	0.08	0.03	0.01	0.08	2.02

Table 3: Results of heavy metal levels in the reservoirs during wet season

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Zone</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>Zn</i>	<i>Mn</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Pb</i>	<i>Cu</i>	<i>Cr</i>
1	1	1.02	0.72	0.02	0.003	0.10	0.03	0.56
2	2	1.13	0.59	0.03	0.01	0.12	0.04	0.67
3	3	1.05	0.67	0.03	0.01	0.10	2.00	0.05

4	Average	1.07	0.66	0.03	0.01	0.11	0.69	0.43
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From minimal to maximal values obtained from analysis, the ranges of the values for the area were presented as below;

Table 4: Ranges for dry season

S/N	Heavy Metals	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3
1	Fe	0.87 - 1.55	0.56 - 0.98	0.80 - 1.08
2	Zn	0.62 - 0.99	0.61 - 0.89	0.00 - 1.01
3	Mn	0.02 - 0.06	0.05 - 0.08	0.05 - 1.08
4	Cd	0.00 - 0.01	0.00 - 0.06	0.00 - 0.07
5	Pb	0.00 - 0.15	0.00 - 0.01	0.01 - 0.02
6	Cu	0.06 - 0.09	0.07 - 0.10	0.07 - 0.09
7	Cr	0.01 - 1.02	2.01 - 2.83	2.56 - 2.85

Table 5: Ranges for wet season

S/N	Heavy Metals	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3
1	Fe	0.78 - 1.59	0.95 - 1.42	0.80 - 1.10
2	Zn	0.55 - 0.97	0.52 - 0.93	0.49 - 1.01
3	Mn	0.01 - 0.05	0.01 - 0.16	0.02 - 0.08
4	Cd	0.00 - 0.01	0.00 - 0.06	0.00 - 0.07
5	Pb	0.01 - 0.16	0.00 - 0.19	0.01 - 0.14
6	Cu	0.01 - 0.08	0.01 - 0.09	0.01 - 0.09
7	Cr	0.33 - 1.03	0.05 - 2.77	0.61 - 2.84

Table 6: Heavy metals comparison with Nigerian and WHO standard

Heavy Metals	Mean		Nigerian Standard	Status		WHO Standard	Status	
	Dry	Wet		Dry	Wet		Dry	Wet
Fe	1.08	1.07	0.03	>	>	< 0.1	>	>
Zn	1.84	0.66	3.00	<	<	0.1	>	>
Mn	0.08	0.03	0.20	<	<	< 0.05	>	<
Cd	0.03	0.01	0.003	>	>	0.003	>	>
Pb	0.01	0.11	0.01	~	>	0.01	~	>
Cu	0.08	0.69	1.00	<	<	2.00	<	<
Cr	2.02	0.43	0.05	>	>	0.05	>	>

Table 7: Results of the heavy metal variation prior season impact

S/N	Zone	Fe	Zn	Mn	Cd	Pb	Cu	Cr
1	1	0.28	0.15	0.02	0.007	- 0.09	0.05	0.21
2	2	- 0.21	0.11	0.04	0.03	- 0.11	0.04	2.06

3	3	- 0.04	0.27	0.11	0.04	- 0.09	- 1.92	2.68
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Seasonal variation in heavy metals for zone one is presented in figure five (5) below;

Figure 5: Heavy metals composition for zone one

Seasonal variation in heavy metals for zone two is presented in figure six (6) below;

Figure 6: Heavy metals composition for zone two

Seasonal variation in heavy metals for zone three is presented in figure seven (7) below;

Figure 7: Heavy metals composition for zone three

Seasonal variation in heavy metals for all zones are presented in figure eight (8) below;

Figure 8: Heavy metals composition for all zones

V. Discussions

From results obtained, both seasons permitted heavy metals concentration in the reservoirs. The dry season was associated to increased concentrations of heavy metals due to its less rainfall and higher temperatures. The wet season, attributed to increased rainfall, provided easy dilution of these heavy metal concentrations in the water. The dilution mobilizes transport avenue through leaching of the heavy metals into the deeper soil layers and eventually into the groundwater reservoirs.

Though the values of these heavy metals were not much in difference from the set standards, and it would take a reasonable quantity of these contagious metallic minerals to pose threats to human health risk symptoms, possible treatments at various sources maybe welcoming for more improved quality standard. Although nature possesses inherent mechanisms to naturally filter and recycle pollutants (Ozioko *et al.*, 2025), understanding the level of these contaminants provides an in-depth guide to possible actions towards improving water quality. According to Robillard *et al.*, (2023), copper (Cu) above 1.3 mg/l is attributable to bitter metallic taste, and, blue-green stains on plumbing fixtures; Iron (Fe) above 0.3 mg/l produces metallic taste, yellowish stains, and stains laundry; Manganese (Mn) above 0.05 mg/l develops bitter taste and, black stains on fixtures and laundry; Lead (Pb) above 0.015 ppm causes nervous disorders and mental impairment (especially in fetuses and infants), kidney damage, blood disorders and hypertension, and low birth weights. EPA, (2025) recorded that Cadmium (Cd) above 0.005 mg/l causes kidney damage, while Chromium (Cr) above 0.1 mg/l causes allergic dermatitis. WHO, (2003) conclusively reported that "drinking water containing zinc at levels above 3 mg/litre tends to be opalescent, develops a greasy film when boiled, and has an undesirable astringent taste". Thus, zinc (Zn) produces milky or cloudy appearance above 3 mg/l. The measurement units of milligrams per liter (mg/l) are equivalent to parts per million (PPM).

Aziz *et al.*, (2023) in their review, presented the various remediation methods for heavy metals removal from water to include; Photocatalysis (possessing high oxidizing potential, can degrade heavy metal complexes, produce no sludge, and capable in degradation of organic complexing

agents), phytoremediation (environmentally benign, and, a slow process), chemical precipitation (low-cost and simple method that effectively removes most heavy metals), reverse osmosis (easily operable, chemical-free, and compatible with other methods), electrochemical treatment (effective metal recycling technology with minimal chemical usage), flotation (low-cost and dewatering), coagulation/flocculation (easy separation of the resulting products and pollutant absorption), membrane filtration (efficient separation and selective at low pressure), adsorption (applicable in wide pH range, high removal efficiency, ease of use, flexibility, cost-effective, and simplicity in design), ion-exchange (low-energy regeneration of resin and economical), and, advanced oxidation processes (formation of in situ reactive radicals, minimal or no chemical usage, and no sludge generation). However the remediation choice, limitations abounds comparatively with the above advantageous attributes.

VI. Conclusion

Arising from the results obtained, the following conclusions were established as presented below; The metal levels of the groundwater reservoirs were affected by the changes in seasons. The variations were as follows: Fe (-0.04 to 0.28), Zn (0.11 to 0.27), Mn (0.02 to 0.11), Cd (0.007 to 0.04), Pb (-0.11 to - 0.09), Cu (-1.92 to 0.05), and, Cr (0.21 to 2.68). Based on the findings, the water sources maybe use for drinking, agriculture and industrial purposes, but should be treated for improvement.

VII. Recommendations

Based on the evaluation, groundwater usage from these reservoirs should be subjected to treatments. The cost can be subsidized by government if it is too expensive for individuals. The treatment may include ion exchange, reverse osmosis, biological denitrification to remove portions of the pollutants from the groundwater reservoirs. The governments, communities, non-governmental organizations (NGO) - businesses, individuals, *etc.*, should contribute in preventing potential land pollution to reduced levels of pollution - contaminants that find their way to the groundwater reservoirs.

Authors Contribution

Okolotu G.I (Conceptualization; Methodology; Visualization; Writing - original draft; Funding; *etc.*)

Udom E.A (Methodology; Resources; Funding; Data curation; Writing - original draft; *etc.*)

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